

THE ROLE OF ADVERBIAL MODIFIERS IN THE SENTENCE AND ITS TYPES

Xidirova Nigora Toshkan qizi

Master student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages

<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejar-v03-i03-p1-15>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th February 2023

Accepted: 04th March 2023

Online: 05th March 2023

KEY WORDS

Adverb, adverbial modifiers, simple sentence, complex sentence, classifications, manner, place, time, reason, degree and so on.

ABSTRACT

This scientific article aims to reveal what adverbial modifiers are, their position, expression, and types in the sentence. The classification of adverbial modifiers by types, their difference from each other, and their role in the sentence are discussed in this article.

The phrase could lead to the incorrect assumption that an adverbial modifier always modifies a verb. Adverbial modifiers can change a section of a sentence that is stated by a verb, an adjective, or an adverb. It would be pointless to attempt to replace the phrase “adverbial mod. Ifier” with another one since it is already well-established. So, the word will remain. In light of what has been mentioned regarding its significance.

Adverbial modifiers can be categorized in a number of different ways:

- 1) Based on what they mean, according to their meaning – not a grammatical classification. However it may acquire some grammatical significance.
- 2) Based on the peculiarities of their morphology; According to their morphological peculiarities – according to the parts of speech and to the phrase patterns. It has also something to do with word order, and stands in a certain relation to the classification according to meaning, adverb, preposition + noun, a noun without a preposition, infinitive or an infinitive phrase
- 3) Based on the nature of their head word. According to the type of their head-word – is the syntactic classification proper. The meaning of the word (phrase) acting as modifier should be compatible with the meaning of the head-word.

The term ‘adverbial modifier’ cannot be said to be a very lucky one, as it is apt to convey erroneous (wrong, incorrect) ideas about the essence of this secondary part. They have nothing to do with adverbs and they modify not only verbs.

Adverbial modifiers (sometimes called adjuncts or adverbials) are verb phrases, phrases, or sentence options that change, comment on, or extend the status of an action or event in relation to entities such as: is a peripheral syntactic element of . Time, place, type, degree, intensity, reason, frequency, etc.

The names of the parts of speech for adverbs and adverbial phrases are very similar. Very often adverbial modifiers are realized by adverbs and adverbial phrases, but they can also be realized by various other syntactical elements, as we will see later. Already confirmed that adverb modifiers are optional elements for all verb phrases and complement types. This syntactic process of adding adverbs to the basic sentence and phrase structure is called verb modification. A verb phrase can contain multiple adverbial modifiers, and there is some flexibility in the possible placement of adverbial modifiers, emphasizing the possibility of mobility.

The grouping of things according to meaning is not in and of itself a grammatical grouping. For instance, the difference between a place- and time-specific adverbial modifier depends on the lexical meaning of the words used as the adverbial modifiers. This categorisation, though, might start to take on some grammatical meaning. Especially when we examine the word order of a sentence and it turns out that one semantic type of adverbial modifier differs from another in this regard. Syntactic theory cannot, then, neglect the categorization of adverbial modifiers according to their meaning.

A word or phrase that modifies another sentence element, usually a verb or an adjective, is known as an adverbial modifier. When used correctly, these modifiers give more details about an activity or a specific section of a sentence, as well as providing an answer to a query about it.

He crossed the bridge swiftly, which is an adverbial modifier.

In this instance, the modifier responds to the query, "How did he cross the bridge?"

An adverbial modifier usually serves to alter another part of a sentence and add more information inside it. Although they occasionally become quite a bit more complex in sentences, these modifiers can be fairly simple. An adverbial modifier can be a single word, usually an adverb, in its simplest form. The "-ly" suffix is frequently added to the end of an adjective to create these modifiers.

An adverbial modifier typically modifies another part of the sentence and adds more details. These modifiers can be pretty simple, yet they can also get quite a bit more complex in sentences. In its most basic form, an adverbial modifier might be a single word, which is typically an adverb. These modifiers are typically made by ending an adjective with the "-ly" suffix.

Types of adverbials.

We have the following 7 types of adverbials in English:

1. Adverbial of manner
2. Adverbial of time
3. Adverbial of reason
4. Adverbial of place
5. Sentence adverbial
6. Adverbial of frequency
7. Adverbial of degree

1. Adverbial of manner

Adverbials of manner modify a verb by talking about the manner in which they take place.

Examples:

- They hurriedly opened the box.
- She quickly grabbed my hand.
- He drove slowly to the wedding.

In these sentences, these adverbs are single words. It can also be phrases and phrases. He spoke politely to the class. I signed up for the program with high hopes. She can kick very fast. When a sentence functions as an adverb, it is called an adverbial phrase. Here, these phrases act as adverbs, telling us how these actions are to be performed. Such phrases are called adverbial phrases of that kind.

- He ate like he hadn't eaten in years.
- She yelled like a ghost.
- John has been speaking to me like his boss.

These are subordinate clauses that act as adverbs. They are called adverbial clauses because they modify the verb and tell us the reason for the action. Note that these adverbial phrases have separate subjects and verbs. So they are clauses, not clauses.

2. Adverbs of Time

Words that modify verbs and indicate the time are called adverbs of time. Example:

- Monika is attending in class.
- I bought these bags yesterday.
- I will call you later.

It doesn't matter if it's a sentence or a sentence. A phrase that modifies a verb by its tense is called a tense adverbial phrase, and a clause that modifies a verb by its tense is called a tense adverbial phrase.

Example:

1. We are opening a new branch soon. (adverb phrase)
2. John came the day before yesterday to discuss something. (adverbial phrase)
3. When the meeting is over, I will order a meal for everyone. (adverb phrase)
4. She left before I got there. (Adverb Phrases)

3. Adverbs of Reason

Adverbs of reason are sentences or sentences that modify verbs by conveying why the verb occurs. A single word cannot function as an adverb of reason. It must be a sentence (adverb principle) or a sentence (adverb principle). Example:

- ❖ He attended boxing classes to learn how to defend himself. (expression)
- ❖ We went to different cities to find investors. (expression)
- ❖ They quit their jobs to start a business together. (sentence)
- ❖ We are saving money so that one day we can start an NGO. (term)
- ❖ Saloni took a day off so that he could rest properly. (clause)

An infinitive that functions as an adverb can also modify an adjective. Here are some examples: It's nice to meet you. (tell us what makes him happy) We were shocked to hear of his passing. (tell us the reason for the state we are in)

4. Adverbs of place

Adverbs of place are words, phrases, and clauses that modify verbs when referring to places.

Example:

1. Bring the child here.
2. Don't go there.
3. It is not prudent. We will meet at the park.
4. No food in class.
5. You can play anywhere you want.
6. I never got to where you went last week.

5. Sentence adverbial

Adverb phrases are simple words that modify a complete sentence. Example: Fortunately, I was there to help you. (Fortunately I was there to help you) (Here, the adverb shows the speaker's attitude towards the situation. It tells what he thinks about the situation.)

For instance: To my surprise, he finished it all in an hour. (Surprisingly he finished it all in an hour) (The whole situation shocked the speaker.) She was clearly coming to the party. (Obviously she's going to the party)

6. Adverbs of frequency

These are words that indicate the frequency of an action. They tell us how often an action is.

Example:

- ❖ We rarely have house parties.
- ❖ I have never seen this movie.
- ❖ She often comes here to eat noodles.
- ❖ Jon visits this temple daily.

Adverbs of frequency are usually one word. But it can also be a sentence. We see each other from time to time. I drank once in the blue moon. Here, the phrase "sometimes" means "sometimes" and the phrase "once in the blue moon" means "rarely".

7. Adverbs of degree

Adverbs of degree show how true something is. It refers to the strength of the word it modifies. It can modify a verb, adjective or adverb.

Example:

- I'm almost done. (Modify the completed verb)
- The coffee is too hot. (Modified hot adjective)
- My sister Jenny has an extremely soft voice. (Modify soft-spoken adjective)
- He kicks a bit fast. (Modify the quick adverb)

To conclude, adverbial modifiers have a great role in the sentence and it is extremely important in both written and spoken speech. Each type of adverbial modifiers has its own characteristics. As can be seen from the above examples, each type of adverbial modifiers has its place in the appropriate sentence. Adverbial modifiers can be categorized in a number of different ways which are very essential for their meaning and the role of sentences.

References:

1. Martin Hummel and Salvador VValera "Adjective Adverb Interfaces in Romance" 2017 pp. 13-46
2. Garton S., Copland F., Burns A. Investigating Global Practices in Teaching English to Young Learners. – UK.: British Council, 2011. – 24 p.
3. Fred Cole Hicks. Strengthening modifiers of adjectives and adverbs in Middle High German. 2012. 386 p
4. Iriskulov M, Tukhtasimov I, Kuldashev A, Theoretical English Grammar, T. Uzkito savdonashr 2020. P.224
5. Гоффоров М. Инглиз тили грамматикаси. — Тошкент: «ТУРОН-ИЌБОЛ», 2006